

1 State of the evidence on the impacts of fishing plastic waste to 2 coastal communities: Protocol for a Systematic Evidence Map

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12 13 Structured abstract

14 **Background:** Fishing plastic waste (FPW) is known to cause multidimensional impacts to coastal
15 communities globally. Detailed information on the environmental, socioeconomic and technical
16 dimensions of effects to coastal communities caused by FPW has yet to be collated and considered in
17 one place. **Methods:** The main aim of this study is to identify, organise and group existing primary
18 evidence of the environmental, social, economic, political, and technical impacts of FPW on coastal
19 communities and identify gaps in our knowledge about which types of FPW are most problematic.
20 **Search Strategy:** We will search several databases across four electronic academic indexes (Web of
21 Science, Scopus, PubMed and EBSCOhost [Business Source Complete, CINAHL Plus, EconLit,
22 GreenFile, and Humanities International Index]). **Eligibility Criteria:** Eligible studies must contain
23 primary research investigating an environmental, social, economic, political, or technical impact of
24 fragments of any size of plastic polymers (macro-, micro-, or nano-) originating from fishing equipment
25 (i.e., capture and ancillary) that has been abandoned, lost, or otherwise discarded in the marine
26 environment, affecting any defined human or non-human (vertebrates, invertebrates, micro-organisms)
27 individual, group or assemblage of individuals, relying on coastal and ocean resources. Environmental
28 impacts include physical and physiological effects to biotic and abiotic elements of marine ecosystems.
29 Social impacts include impacts to community health and wellbeing. Economic impacts include impacts
30 to livelihood and trade. Political impacts include responses from local or regional governments to

31 address FPW. Technical impacts include effects to techniques employed by fisherfolk or to the
32 management of FPW at the local level. **Screening & Extraction:** Our search was optimised on Cadima.
33 Articles will be screened at title and abstract, before a full-text review. All articles will be screened by
34 a single reviewer, with two additional reviewers assessing articles for consistency. One out of ten
35 articles will be screened by two additional reviewers in duplicate as a quality control. Data extraction
36 will be performed on all articles included at full text, and articles that do not meet the eligibility criteria
37 will be excluded. All articles excluded at full text will be confirmed by the two additional reviewers.
38 **Study Mapping & Reporting:** Results will be published in a narrative summary and visualised in a
39 publicly available, user-friendly, interactive and interrogable evidence map on Tableau.

40

41 **1. Introduction**

42 **1.1. Background and Rationale**

43 Plastics are synthetic or semi-synthetic organic polymers that have become entrenched in modern-day
44 society due to their beneficial characteristics, such as their affordability, durability, lightweightness,
45 mouldability and insulating capabilities (Derraik, 2002; Thompson *et al.*, 2009). A consequence of these
46 characteristics is that plastics are now undervalued, often being mass-produced for products with a short
47 lifespan, resulting in a rapid accumulation of plastic waste. This, coupled with inadequate waste
48 management systems that fail to capture the various plastic wastes and their embedded values, has led
49 to plastic waste becoming a ubiquitous pollutant in our environment.

50 Geyer estimates that between 1950-2017, only 10% of all plastics ever made had been recycled, 14%
51 had been incinerated, and 76% had been discarded into landfills (Geyer, 2020). This issue is more dire
52 in low- to middle-income countries, which tend to have poorer waste management infrastructure,
53 resulting in a higher prevalence of mismanaged waste. Meijer *et al.* estimated that globally, 67.5 trillion
54 metric tonnes (t) of mismanaged plastic waste are produced annually, with 1.5% of this leaking into the
55 ocean (Meijer *et al.*, 2021). It is now acknowledged that plastics make up the majority of waste present
56 in the marine environment (Gregory and Ryan, 1997; Barnes *et al.*, 2009; Galgani, Hanke and Maes,
57 2015).

58 Although only 20% of plastics entering the ocean are thought to originate from marine-based activities,
59 fishing gear accounts for 10% of marine plastic waste and represents the highest proportion of
60 macroplastics floating on the ocean's surface (Thomas, Dorey and Obaidullah, 2019; Morales-Caselles
61 *et al.*, 2021). In some regions, fishing plastic waste (FPW) makes up the majority of litter present.
62 Specifically, it accounted for 100% of litter found in the North and Northeast Faroe-Shetland Channels
63 and >85% of litter found in the Condor Seamount, Hatton Bank and Wyville-Thomson Ridge (Pham *et*

64 *al.*, 2014). Moreover, 52% of the plastics found in the Great Pacific Garbage Patch originate from
65 fishing activities, of which fishing nets formed 86% of the 42kt of megaplastics (>50cm) present
66 (Lebreton *et al.*, 2018; Thomas, Dorey and Obaidullah, 2019). Despite this, current research focuses
67 predominantly on land-based sources of plastics.

68 FPW has been shown to have physical and physiological impacts on marine biota and coastal
69 environments and, consequently, human populations (Jones, 1995; Dau et al., 2009; Macfadyen,
70 Huntington and Cappell, 2009; Link, Segal and Casarini, 2019; Watson et al., 2022). Coastal
71 communities in low-middle-income countries are heavily reliant on marine ecosystems for their
72 livelihoods, including sustenance, trade, tourism, and cultural value (Rao *et al.*, 2016; Robertson and
73 Midway, 2019; Wei, Xu and Wall, 2023) and are vulnerable to changes in the marine environment
74 (Aswani *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, with most the world's capture fisheries being based in these regions,
75 coastal communities here may be at greater risk from the effects of this pollution (Apete, Martin and
76 Iacovidou, 2024). Understanding how FPW impact them is necessary to devise solutions with these
77 communities and for governments to design effective policy interventions.

78 Recent literature that explores the impacts of marine debris on coastal communities largely overlooks
79 FPW (UN, 2016b, p. 8). While reviews have been carried out on the impacts of abandoned fishing gear,
80 none focus specifically on gear made from plastics, despite the consensus that plastics are the dominant
81 material for this equipment (Jones, 1995; Macfadyen, Huntington and Cappell, 2009; Link, Segal and
82 Casarini, 2019; Watson *et al.*, 2022). These reviews typically analyse items such as lines, nets and ropes
83 but omit the impacts of associated equipment, such as polystyrene storage boxes and plastic ice bags
84 used for storage and preservation (Do and Armstrong, 2023). Furthermore, most studies emphasise
85 environmental impacts, with limited attention to the broader impacts on coastal ecosystems, particularly
86 in developing countries. Although existing research has identified negative impacts on provisioning,
87 supporting and cultural services, none addressed regulating services. In addition, there is limited recent
88 literature on the socioeconomic impacts of FPW in coastal communities (Jones, 1995; Macfadyen,
89 Huntington and Cappell, 2009). In many of these communities, there is a heavy reliance on the marine
90 environment for service provision, yet they face increasing pressure from inadequate solid waste
91 management systems (Arifin *et al.*, 2023; Daniel and Thomas, 2023). This underlines the urgent need
92 for addressing both the environmental and socioeconomic dimensions of FPW, particularly in regions
93 with high dependency on marine ecosystems and limited waste infrastructure.

94 The growing prevalence of FPW in the marine environment highlights the crucial need for a systematic
95 approach to understanding its systemic impacts on coastal communities. Systematic evidence maps
96 (SEM) provide an effective method for amassing and assessing the existing evidence base, identifying
97 knowledge gaps, and guiding future research priorities. Such analyses can reveal critical blind spots in
98 our understanding of systemic failures related to FPW pollution and inform targeted interventions to

99 tackle these issues. For coastal communities, this approach is particularly valuable in tackling pollution
 100 challenges holistically. SEM also serves as a key step in employing a systems-based approach, helping
 101 to unpack the drivers of FPW pollution and generate useful evidence to support effective interventions.
 102 This SEM aims to provide a comprehensive, multi-dimensional perspective on the impacts of FPW on
 103 coastal communities. Our preliminary understanding and a priori assumptions of this system were
 104 informed by a narrative review used to produce a causal loop diagram (CLD; **Figure 1**) (Apete, Martin
 105 and Iacovidou, 2024). This has informed the development of the SEM protocol.

106
 107 **Figure 1: Causal loop diagram of the known and the known unknown environmental (green),**
 108 **health (purple) and socio-economic (blue) effects of fishing plastic pollution in the marine**
 109 **environment. Known-unknown causal links are joined by a dashed line. Paler nodes represent**
 110 **effects where all causal links are known unknowns. ALDFG = abandoned, lost, or otherwise**
 111 **discarded fishing gear; TPOCs = toxic persistent organic pollutants.; MP = microplastics. This is**
 112 **found here: [https://kumu.io/larisha1/interconnections-between-socio-ecological-impacts-of-](https://kumu.io/larisha1/interconnections-between-socio-ecological-impacts-of-fishing-plastic-waste#untitled-map)**
 113 **[fishing-plastic-waste#untitled-map](https://kumu.io/larisha1/interconnections-between-socio-ecological-impacts-of-fishing-plastic-waste#untitled-map)**

114
 115 Understanding the causal connections between these impacts is beyond the scope of this SEM. Instead,
 116 the body of evidence retrieved will inform systems-based analyses where it is triangulated and
 117 integrated with contextual data from case study sites collected through semi-structured interviews. By
 118 mapping the available evidence, we will widen and improve our understanding of the complex
 119 interrelationships within these environmental, technological, political, economic and social sub-

120 systems. The findings will enable practitioners to identify knowledge gaps and potential positive and
121 negative feedback loops, reducing the risk of adopting a siloed approach to problem-solving, thereby
122 fostering integrated, sustainable solutions.

123

124 **1.2. Definitions and Disambiguation of Terms**

125 **1.2.1. Coastal Communities**

126 There are many definitions of coastal communities in the literature, specifically referring to human
127 settlements (**Table 1**). A commonly used definition incorporates a 100-kilometre (km) inland boundary
128 based on analyses of human population distribution, which revealed a steep population density gradient
129 over this distance (Small and Nicholls, 2003; Small and Cohen, 2004). However, for our systematic
130 evidence mapping, our focus is not on geographic proximity but rather on populations and communities
131 whose livelihoods are directly dependent on coastal and marine resources. While populations and
132 communities beyond the 100km threshold are often bound to inland activities and may not be linked to
133 the coast socio-economically (e.g., through fishing or cultural identity), others may depend on coastal
134 systems/infrastructure (e.g., inland agricultural communities dependent on estuaries). Therefore, it is
135 important to consider populations and communities reliance on surrounding natural resources as
136 emphasised in definitions by Green 2.0 (2022) the Coastal Communities Alliance (2024), particularly
137 when investigating the socioeconomic, political, and technical impacts. These natural resources include
138 the biotic and abiotic elements of marine and coastal ecosystems, which directly influence the
139 ecosystem services available to coastal communities.

140

141 **Table 1: Definitions of coastal communities found in the literature**

Definition	Source
Populations within 100 horizontal km of the coastline and 100 vertical meters of sea level.	(Small and Nicholls, 2003)
Any coastal settlement within a(n English) local authority area whose boundaries include (English) foreshore, including local authorities whose boundaries only include estuarine foreshore. Coastal settlements include seaside towns, ports and other areas which have a clear connection to the coastal economy.	(Coastal Communities Alliance, 2024)
Coastal populations are those living within 100 km of the coast, and excluding countries without territory within 100 km of a coastline measured using an Azimuthal Equidistant (world) projection.	(Barbier, 2015)
Percentage of total population living within 100 km of the coastline.	(UN, 2017; UNEP, 2017)

Residents living within 100 km of the shore. (Maul and Duedall, 2021)
 One that lives near the coast and/or utilizes coastal resources and the ocean for its livelihood in a manner shaped by cultural heritage or economic needs. (Green 2.0, 2022) – environmental racial diversity NGO

People living within 100 km from the coast. (Barros *et al.*, 2023)

142

143 Further for this study, our understanding of “coastal communities” will be defined as “*individuals or*
 144 *groups of individuals living near the coast and/or relying on coastal and ocean resources for their*
 145 *livelihoods, in ways influenced by cultural heritage or economic need, and interconnected with the*
 146 *ecosystems that support them*”. This definition accounts for both the geographical proximity and the
 147 socioeconomic, cultural and ecological interconnections on which the livelihoods and well-being of
 148 coastal communities rely.

149 **1.2.2. Fishing Plastic Waste**

150 Currently, there is no universally accepted definition for “fishing plastic waste”. To address this gap,
 151 we developed a definition by analysing existing definitions of fishing plastic equipment, referred to
 152 here as "fishing plastics" or "fishing gear", and reviewing how FPW is characterised in the literature.

153 The definitions of fishing gear (**Table 2**) vary in the specificity of the components included. However,
 154 they consistently agree that *fishing gear refers to any equipment or combination of components used*
 155 *or capable of being used to capture, control for subsequent capture, or harvest marine or freshwater*
 156 *organisms and biological resources*. Most descriptions of fishing gear are derived from the
 157 International Standard Statistical Classification of Fishing Gear (ISSCFG) (He *et al.*, 2021), which was
 158 designed to support fisheries and marine conservation research. The ISSCFG classifies fishing gear
 159 based on physical characteristics, operational methods, and fish capture mechanisms. The major types
 160 of fishing gear and their material compositions are summarised in **Table S1** (*Annex 1*).

161

162 **Table 2: Definitions of fishing gear found in the literature**

Definition of Fishing Gear	Source
A fishing gear is any physical device or part thereof, or combination of items that may be placed on or in the water or on the seabed with the intended purpose of capturing or controlling for subsequent capture or harvesting marine or freshwater organisms.	The International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL), Annex V (MEPC, 2011)

<p>“Fishing gear” means any net or other implement or means used or capable of being used for the harvesting of marine resources.</p>	<p>Namibia’s Marine Resources Act, 27 of 2000 (Republic of Namibia, 2000)</p>
<p>Fishing gear means any equipment, implement or other thing that can be used in the act of fishing, and includes any fishing net, rope, line, float, trap, hook, winch, or associated boat or aircraft.</p>	<p>Fisheries Act No. 10 of 2014, (Republic of Vanuatu, 2014)</p>
<p>“Sea fishing equipment” means (a) fishing nets or any other equipment used during sea fishing (including, for example, equipment used to navigate, or to deter animals that are not intended to be caught), or (b) equipment used to monitor sea fishing.</p>	<p>Fisheries Act 2020, (UK Government, 2020)</p>
<p>“Fishing gear” means any item or piece of equipment that is used in fishing or aquaculture to target, capture or rear marine biological resources or that is floating on the sea surface, and is deployed with the objective of attracting and capturing or of rearing such marine biological resources.</p>	<p>Directive (EU) 2019/904 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment (European Parliament, Council of the European Union, 2019)</p>
<p>Fishing gear includes any net, line, pot, bob, trap, dredge, apparatus, device, or other thing that is used or is capable of being used for the purposes of taking fish.</p>	<p>Fisheries (Amateur Fishing) Regulations 2013 New Zealand (Governor-General, 2013)</p>
<p>Facilities and equipment or other objects that are used for fishing.</p>	<p>Ministerial Regulation 33/PERMEN-KP/2021 – (Minister of Marine Affairs And Fisheries of The Republic of Indonesia, 2021)</p>

163

164 Defining fishing plastic becomes more complicated when looking at how FPW is characterised in the
 165 literature. Fishing plastics also encompass ancillary items used in fishing activities, such as buoys,
 166 gloves, fish storage boxes, strapping bands, plastic bottles carrying stroke oil, and plastic ice bags for
 167 fish preservation that become waste (**Table S2** in *Annex 2*).

168 In the literature, FPW is characterised as materials, components and products that have been abandoned,
 169 lost, or discarded in the environment and are associated with the act of fishing (Claereboudt, 2004;
 170 Edyvane *et al.*, 2004; Moriarty *et al.*, 2016; UNEP, 2016; Consoli *et al.*, 2019; European Commission,
 171 2019; Simeonova and Chaturkova, 2020; GESAMP, 2021; Pinheiro *et al.*, 2021, 2023; ICES, 2022;
 172 Nguyen *et al.*, 2022; Watson *et al.*, 2022). These ancillary items are necessary for the handling, storage,
 173 and preservation of captured or harvested marine organisms but are often made from polymers also
 174 commonly found in marine debris of terrestrial origin (e.g., polystyrene being used for fish storage
 175 boxes, as well as food containers). In some fisheries, particularly small-scale and artisanal activities,
 176 marine resources are brought directly to shore for sale, often using the same plastic materials used
 177 during fishing (e.g., fish boxes, gloves) (UN, 2016a, p. 4; Pardie and Champion, 2022; Cunha *et al.*,
 178 2023). As this study focuses on the global impacts of FPW on coastal communities, particularly those
 179 dependent on small-scale, artisanal fisheries, our definition includes plastics used for storing and

180 preserving the catch during direct sales on shore. Excluding this aspect risks overlooking a critical
181 component, potentially leading to an incomplete understanding of what encompasses FPW and,
182 subsequently, their environmental and socio-economic impacts, leading to partial or ineffective
183 solutions.

184 Considering these definitions and conditions, we developed the following working definition of FPW
185 as “*a piece, part or combination of equipment made from plastic polymers that are used or capable of*
186 *being used to capture, control for subsequent capture, or harvest, marine or freshwater organisms,*
187 *including ancillary plastic items that support these activities or are used for the storage and*
188 *preservation of these organisms until sold or allocated for personal consumption by the fisher, that has*
189 *been abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded in the marine or coastal environment”.*

190 This definition includes only ancillary items explicitly linked to fishing practices (e.g., gloves, storage boxes, ice bags).
191 It includes plastic items used to store gear during fishing activities, as well as repurposed consumer
192 plastics used in fishing activities (e.g., plastic bottles repurposed as bailing containers). This definition
193 excludes plastics associated with fish farming equipment and aquaculture. The broad definition is
194 intended to ensure that variation in how FPW is described in literature does not hinder the extraction of
195 relevant data.

196 **1.2.3. Multidimensional impacts**

197 This SEM will explore five key dimensions of impact: (i) environmental; (ii) social; (iii) economic; (iv)
198 technical; and (v) political impacts. These dimensions align with the five interacting sub-systems of the
199 ‘five levels of information’, or ‘5LoI’ framework of the Complex Value Optimisation for Resource
200 Recovery (CVORR) systems-based tool (Iacovidou *et al.*, 2020; **Figure 2**).

201 This facilitates a holistic understanding of the complex interrelationships within these systems.

202

203

204 **Figure 2: The ‘5LoI’ (five levels of information), a conceptual framework that enables the**
 205 **understanding of the dynamics, drivers and barriers of resource recovery systems; Source:**
 206 **(Iacovidou *et al.*, 2020).**

207

208 Environmental impacts fall within the 1st level of information, the ‘Natural environment and
 209 provisioning services’. The SEM will explore the impacts of FPW on ecosystem health (i.e., marine
 210 organisms and their habitats), biodiversity and ecosystem services that coastal communities depend on
 211 for their well-being (via ecosystem services).

212 Technical impacts fall within the 2nd level of information, ‘Technologies, infrastructure and innovation
 213 level’. Technical impacts relate to a "technique", i.e., a specialised method or procedure, and challenges
 214 related to fishing gear functionality, fishing activities or operations and waste management systems.
 215 Therefore, technical effects to coastal communities once plastic fishing gear becomes waste/they are
 216 exposed to FPW in the environment include changes in the way communities conduct fishing activities
 217 (e.g., reduced functionality of gear, altered fishing techniques) or methods of dealing with this waste at
 218 end-of-use/end-of-life (e.g., repair, repurposing, recycling, collection for disposal, energy recovery).
 219 This may also relate to what indigenous knowledge and technical skills may have been lost at the end
 220 of the use/life stage due to replacing traditional fishing gear with plastic fishing gear.

221 Political impacts support the 3rd level of information: ‘Governance, regulatory framework and political
 222 landscape’. This refers to policy responses from the government in coastal regions to address FPW.
 223 Ultimately, any policy proposed in response to FPW will have consequences for the region’s inhabitants.

224 Economic impacts support the 4th level of information, ‘Activities performed by businesses and the
225 market’. The SEM will include the impacts of FPW on livelihoods, including financial implications
226 from the presence of FPW on individuals and the broader coastal communities.

227 Social impacts support the 5th level of information, ‘Patterns of behaviour related to meeting human and
228 societal needs’. The SEM will focus on the impacts of FPW on human well-being and community
229 dynamics, including cultural aspects and perspectives on FPW.

230 **1.3. Objectives**

231 Well-formulated research statements are critical for ensuring the accuracy and coherence of other
232 review components, including the literature search strategy, data extraction, synthesis, and presentation
233 of findings. The PEO (Population, Exposure, Outcome) framework (Moola *et al.*, 2015) is a widely
234 used tool for exploring associations between specific exposures and outcomes, particularly in
235 qualitative research.

236 **Our research question is articulated as follows:** What are the environmental, social, technical,
237 economic and political impacts of FPW-associated pollution on coastal communities?

238 Using the PEO framework (**Table 3**), the specific objectives of this SEM are to:

- 239 1. Identify, group and organise existing primary evidence on the multidimensional
240 (environmental, social, economic, political, technical) impacts (outcomes) of FPW (exposure)
241 on coastal communities, inclusive of the ecosystems these communities rely on (population).
- 242 2. Present the evidence in a user-friendly format, including an interactive online cause-effect
243 diagram and dashboard that will be made publicly accessible to facilitate knowledge sharing.
- 244 3. Identify knowledge gaps and evidence clusters across taxa (population), FPW types (exposure),
245 and multidimensional effects (outcomes) to inform future research needs and/or analysis.

247 **Table 3: PEO framework developed for this protocol - Population, Exposure, Outcome**

Element of PEO framework	Description of the PEO element developed for this protocol
Population	Individuals or groups of individuals living near the coast and/or relying on coastal and ocean resources for their livelihoods, in ways influenced by cultural heritage or economic need, and interconnected with the ecosystems that support them.
Exposure	A piece, part or combination of equipment made from plastic polymers that are used or capable of being used to capture, control for subsequent capture, or harvest, marine or freshwater organisms, including ancillary plastic items that support these activities or are used for the storage and preservation of these organisms until sold or allocated for personal

consumption by the fisher, that has been abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded in the marine or coastal environment.

Outcomes

Environmental impacts caused by the presence and exposure of human and non-human populations or communities to FPW in the marine and coastal environments. This includes physical harm to marine life (e.g., entanglement and ingestion, habitat damage), toxicological impacts (e.g., chemicals leaching, microplastics), disruption of ecosystem services (e.g., impact on marine food web and flora), contribution to climatic change (e.g., greenhouse gases emissions).

Social impacts of the presence or interaction of FPW with human and non-human populations or communities in the marine and coastal environments. This includes impacts on health and well-being or coastal communities.

Technical impacts arising from the presence or interaction of FPW in the marine and coastal environments. These include technical challenge such as damage to fishing equipment (e.g., gear entanglement, gear loss and equipment degradation due to wear and tear), repair and recycling.

Economic impacts to individuals, groups of individuals or economies caused by the presence or interaction of FPW in the marine and coastal environments. These include impacts on livelihoods, fisheries, tourism, and economic activities dependent on healthy marine and coastal ecosystems.

Political impacts resulting from the presence of FPW in the marine and coastal environments, particularly on local policy and governance. This may include the influence on local government activities, regulations and initiatives aimed at managing the impacts of FPW on ecosystems or managing and reducing FPW.

248 2. Methods

249 This protocol was drafted following the updated 2015 PRISMA-P guidelines (Preferred Reporting Items
250 for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols; *Annex 3*) (Moher *et al.*, 2015; Page *et al.*, 2021)
251 and giving due consideration to the recommendations for the Conduct of Systematic Reviews in
252 Toxicology and Environmental Health Research (COSTER) (Whaley *et al.*, 2020).

253 2.1. Information sources

254 Peer-reviewed academic literature will be found by searching on Web of Science (WoS), Scopus and
255 Pubmed electronic indexes, as well as Business Source Complete, CINAHL Plus, EconLit, GreenFile,
256 and Humanities International Index via the EBSCOHost Platform. All databases will be accessed using
257 the University College London subscription (as of December 2024). Pilot searches demonstrated that
258 this combination of databases provides adequate coverage for the diverse range of outcomes to be
259 explored. Details of each database's disciplinary coverage can be found in the supplementary material
260 (*Annex 4*). The searches will be complemented by direct citation searching (i.e., snowballing),
261 conducted using the TARCiS checklist developed by Hirst and colleagues (Hirt *et al.*, 2024). Springer

262 was considered; however, it yielded an unmanageable number of results (>500,000). Conversely,
263 Anthropology Plus, SocIndex, and Child Development and Adolescent Studies via the EBSCOHost
264 Platform, and JSTOR were also considered, but all yielded an insufficient number of relevant results
265 (<3%).

266 All indexes will be searched using title, abstract and keyword fields. This will be achieved on WoS by
267 searching by Topic in the core collection and all databases subscribed to by University College London
268 (as of December 2024). If a search update is required, the search will be repeated, however, limited to
269 studies published since the date of the last search.

270 Grey literature searches will be manually conducted on repositories of The World Bank Group, the
271 United Nations (UN), the Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD), as well
272 as Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) reports and published research available via the Google
273 search engine.

274 Literature screening will be managed and coordinated with the support of the freely available online
275 tool CADIMA, established in a close collaboration between the Julius Kühn-Institut and the
276 Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (Kohl *et al.*, 2018). The reference manager, Citavi (Swiss
277 Academic Software, 2023), will be used to support the retrieval of full texts of studies. Data will be
278 collected and presented using Microsoft Excel.

279 **2.2. Search Strategy**

280 We developed search strings for each database to reflect our PEO framework in collaboration with a
281 librarian specialist (JMP). Population terms were developed relating to aspects of the study subject (i.e.,
282 community, coastal, environment, organism) and species group (i.e., human, animal, plant, bacteria,
283 fungi). As plastic is the standard material used in fishing gear, it is common for titles and abstracts not
284 to reference plastic materials in papers related to the effects of fishing plastic waste. Titles and abstracts
285 either describe the effects of 1) specific items of gear, with no explicit mention of fishing or material,
286 2) “fishing-related” pollution, or 3) marine debris, with no mention of fishing or material. Therefore, it
287 was important for exposure terms to sufficiently capture this variation by including general terms for
288 fishing plastics (e.g., fishing gear, fishing nets, rope), terms related to the source of the item (e.g., fisher*
289 related, originating from fishing, derived from fishing), the material (e.g., fishing *plastic, plastic
290 polymer names), and waste terms (e.g., pollut*, derelict). Proximity operators (e.g., fisher* NEAR
291 origin) were employed here to capture these items.

292 Pilot searches revealed a need to group microplastic terms with waste terms, as due to these intrinsically
293 being waste abstracts, they did not tend to use waste terms (e.g., litter, pollution) to describe them. To
294 capture relevant literature where fishing plastic waste is described as marine debris in the abstract, we
295 also searched for fishing-related terms in the keywords field. No search limitation (i.e., NOT terms)

296 were used to prevent excluding studies reporting on more than one population/exposure/outcome. The
297 search was not restricted by language; however, as the search was conducted in English, a title and
298 abstract in English were required to assess the relevance of the study.

299 A comprehensive list of outcome terms was devised related to health effects (e.g., inflammation,
300 oxidative stress, genotoxicity, apoptosis, necrosis), ecologically relevant effects (e.g., survival,
301 reproduction, growth, development, behaviour, invasive species, greenhouse gas emissions), social
302 effects (e.g., culture, recreation, education), economic effects (e.g., econom*, livelihood, income),
303 political (e.g., govern*, poli*, legislation), and technical effects (e.g., technique, dispose, reuse,
304 repurpose). Terms related to known methods of estimating these outcomes were also used (e.g., LCA,
305 cost*benefit). Outcome terms were included as they effectively refined the results without
306 compromising a significant number of relevant papers (2% relevant papers missed). Terms were
307 searched for individually on each database to confirm their relevance, then combined with Boolean and
308 proximity operators to devise a sufficiently sensitive whilst selective strategy (*Table S4 in Annex 5*).

309 Details of the performance-piloted search terms and strings and the agreed final search strings can be
310 found in *Annex 6*. As it is not possible for any search string to capture all existing literature or to be
311 completely free of bias, we undertook a validation exercise using a subset of articles (n=30) identified
312 as relevant to the objectives of this study (*Annex 7*). These articles were selected during the initial
313 scoping search using expert knowledge or due to their inclusion in prior articles reviewing the evidence
314 of environmental, economic, social, and/or technical/technological effects of marine plastic pollution
315 (Browne et al., 2015; Li, Tse and Fok, 2016; Stelfox, Hudgins and Sweet, 2016; Agamuthu et al., 2019;
316 Angiolillo and Fortibuoni, 2020; Kumar et al., 2021; Costa et al., 2022; Hernandez et al., 2022; Watson
317 et al., 2022; Agarwala, 2023; Gilman et al., 2023; Nama et al., 2023; Kibria, 2024). They include papers
318 related to each outcome category and contain varying levels of detail in the title/abstract describing the
319 type of fishing plastic waste. Comparing the list of relevant articles to articles retrieved using our search
320 string on WoS, we achieved a retrieval rate of 87%. This increased to 93% when searching in Scopus,
321 PubMed or EBSCOHost for missed articles. Thus, we are confident that our search strategy is robust
322 enough to identify the body of evidence relevant to our research aims.

323 Grey literature search strings will be adapted to fit the functionalities and filters available for retrieving
324 results from these sources.

325 **2.3. Eligibility Criteria**

326 The PEO statement (Table 4) informed the development of clear inclusion and exclusion criteria to
327 ensure transparent and reproducible study eligibility screening. These criteria enable a systematic
328 approach to study selection for the SEM.

329 This SEM is focused on evidence of real-world impacts on coastal communities and the natural
 330 environment they depend on. Thus, laboratory, in vitro, and silico studies were excluded, as they
 331 typically rely on controlled conditions, technical proxies, or sample types that may not reflect the
 332 complex, real-world socio-technical, and environmental contexts relevant to this evidence mapping.
 333 Including such studies could introduce context-specific biases and limit the generalisability of findings
 334 to field-based, observational settings.

335

336 **Table 4:** Eligibility criteria for inclusion and exclusion of the PEO framework.

PEO element	<i>Inclusion criteria</i>	<i>Exclusion criteria</i>
Population	<p>All the following must be true:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any defined individual, group or assemblage of individuals or species • human or non-human (Vertebrates including humans, Invertebrates, Micro-organisms) • Relying on coastal and ocean resources 	<p>If any of these is true, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undefined group(s) e.g. global, nationals or regional population
Exposure	<p>All the following must be true:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fragments of any size of plastic polymers (macro-, micro-, or nano-) • Polymer types: ... • Waste (no longer in active use) • Origin attributed to previous use as fishing gear • Repurposed consumer plastics used in fishing activities • Plastic items used to store gear during fishing activities 	<p>If any of these is true, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodegradable plastic or natural polymers • Still in active use • Waste of unspecified origin • Waste from activities other than fishing • Waste from fish farms and aquaculture • Waste or fragments from boats and ships regardless of whether they are used in fishing or other activities.
Outcomes	<p>Any of the following is true for:</p> <p>Environmental impacts, Field, in situ or observational study measuring any of the following.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • physical harm to marine life caused by macroplastic (e.g., entanglement and ingestion, ghost fishing, smothering and habitat damage). These do not need to describe a population- 	<p>If any of these is true, the study is excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducted under controlled laboratory conditions • In vitro or in silico experiments

level impact to be accepted, as plastics of this size have inherent physiological effects (i.e., gastrointestinal tract function, motility, or presence of a foreign object attached to the body).

- impacts to marine biotic and abiotic elements.
- disruption of ecosystem services

If these are the only outcomes measured, the study is excluded:

- Abundance of any type of plastic
- Ingestion or inhalation on NMPs
- Characteristics of nano- or microplastics ingested or inhaled by an organism

OR **Social impacts**, objectively measured or perceived related to.

- Health and well-being
- Human rights,
- Safety,
- Justice,
- Culture and recreation,
- Education,
- Access to services
- Working life (e.g. labour rights, working conditions)

If these are the only outcomes, the study is excluded:

- estimate(s) of future impacts
- theoretical studies

OR **Economic impacts**, objectively measured or perceived on.

- Livelihoods,
- Trade
- Any financial costs/benefits

If these are the only outcomes, the study is excluded:

- estimate(s) of future impacts
- theoretical studies

OR **Political impacts**, including.

- Local or regional responses (e.g., initiatives/schemes, action plans, policies, legislation)
- Responses at the interface of local and national policy that provide empirical insights from cross-scale governance structures from local, national and global scale.
- Enforcement of new or existing responses

If these are the only outcomes measured, the study is excluded:

- Exclusively national and multilateral governmental responses
- Outcomes of governmental responses on FPW based on stakeholder perceptions

OR **Technical impacts**, including.

- Local techniques employed for fishing gear or active fishing
 - Local management at the end-of-use/end-of-life stage
- If these are the only outcomes measured, the study is excluded:
- Global, international, corporate or national techniques
 - Technological solutions
-

337

338 **2.3.1. Refinement via Piloting of the Screening Process**

339 A first consistency check was conducted to develop and refine the eligibility criteria. All search results
340 were imported into Cadima, where duplicate records were removed, leaving a total of 9,581 unique
341 references. Three reviewers piloted the Title and Abstract screening by applying the initial eligibility
342 criteria to the titles and abstracts of 7.83% (n=750) of the results, as this is the maximum allowed on
343 Cadima. This resulted in 121 papers being progressed to full text screening; therefore, we estimated
344 ~1400 papers may still be progressed for full text screening. This high number of eligible studies would
345 be challenging to extract data from within the resources allocated to this project. It is common for
346 literature exploring the impacts of marine plastics (especially microplastics and smaller) not to include
347 the source of the plastic in the abstract. A permissive interpretation of the eligibility criteria would
348 further introduce uncertainty and weaken our analysis of the evidence. To limit this, we sought to refine
349 our eligibility criteria to reduce the 89 of 121 eligible rated unclear at the Title and Abstract screening
350 stage.

351

352 The reviewers noted a high occurrence of microplastic papers that did not explicitly refer to FPW in the
353 title or abstract, so needed to be progressed to full text screening to determine their relevance. To reduce
354 this, microplastic papers will only progress to full text screening if they relate to direct impacts to marine
355 biotic (i.e., impacts following ingestion/inhalation) and abiotic elements. In addition, many studies were
356 identified that made inferences about potential impacts in the abstract after solely characterising or
357 estimating the abundance of fishing plastic waste in the environment. It was decided that only studies
358 that directly investigate impacts would be accepted.

359 Furthermore, studies on political impacts will only be progressed that impact on our defined 'coastal
360 communities' population (i.e., at the local level). Studies at the interface of local and national policy
361 will be included if they provide empirical insights from cross-scale governance structures from local,
362 national and global scales. Whilst those exclusively at the national and multilateral levels will be
363 excluded. Studies reporting on the outcomes of governmental responses on FPW (e.g., government
364 clean-up project), based on stakeholder perceptions will also be excluded.

365 Finally, only studies on technical impacts to fishing technique and management of FPW at end-of-
366 use/end-of-life will be progressed. Studies on technological impacts will be excluded.

367 A second consistency check was conducted applying the new eligibility criteria to the 121 progressed
368 studies using Microsoft Excel (*Annex 8*). This process reduced the number of progressed studies to 55.
369 Further refinement of the search strings to reduce ambiguous studies produced 6,237 results. Applying
370 the outcome of the consistency check (depicted in *Annex 9*) we estimate ~400 papers may still be
371 progressed to full text screening. The logic underlying the application of the eligibility criteria is
372 detailed in **Table 4**.

373 **2.4. Study selection**

374 Title-abstract and full-text screening will be conducted by LA in Cadima. Title-abstract screening will
375 be set up with a 10% overlap (i.e., LA will screen 100% of the studies and 10% of the studies will be
376 screened in duplicate by OM and EI) as a quality control step. The full text of studies included after
377 title-abstract screening will be retrieved and screened in Cadima - again with a 10% overlap as a quality
378 control check while one screener (LA) conducts most of the screening. Discrepancies between
379 reviewers will be resolved through discussion between reviewers as soon as they arise to allow for the
380 rectification of any systematic error or drift in the interpretation of eligibility criteria to be addressed as
381 soon as detected. An unexplained high rate of discrepancies (> 5%, checked weekly) may trigger a
382 second round of screening as a corrective step. We will report the recorded discrepancy rates. The
383 reasons for the exclusion of studies after the assessment of the full text will be recorded.

384 Multiple reports of the same study (e.g. multiple publications, conference abstracts, etc.) will not be
385 excluded, but instead, the methodological information from each of the reports will be collated as part
386 of the data recording process as one unit of evidence.

387

388 **2.5. Data extraction and data items**

389 A data extraction template in Microsoft Excel was developed, piloted and revised following the piloting
390 exercise. Three reviewers individually extracted data from a sample of papers (n=3) identified as
391 relevant during the second consistency check. The results of these individual data extraction exercises
392 were compared to ensure parity (*Annex 10*). This piloting exercise generated important discussions
393 about what one unit of evidence should consist of and avoid the multiplication of rows. Following
394 piloting, it was agreed that capturing detailed information under each outcome was neither necessary
395 nor feasible to meet the aims of this systematic evidence map. We decided to capture broad categories
396 and allow the selection multiple entries rather than triggering a separate entry (new row). Google Forms
397 was tested to achieve this and rejected. We found using a Visual Basic for Applications (VBA) code in

398 Excel (Annex 11) to allow the selection of multiple items in drop down lists to be most appropriate for
399 the subsequent production of Tableau visualisations and dashboards. Full guidance on the cells in which
400 multiple entries are permitted can be found in the “Instructions” sheet of the Data Extraction Template
401 (Annex 10). One reviewer (LA) will extract data from the included records, and 1 in 10 will be extracted
402 in duplicate in parallel by OVM or EI as a quality control step. The error rate will be checked weekly,
403 with a focus on entries which have a material impact on further analyses of the database, specifically
404 consistent categorisation and completeness of extraction. Here, estimating an error rate is more complex
405 and will require qualitative judgement on when an error rate should trigger duplicate extraction of data
406 from studies not included in the quality control check. We will report error rates, differentiating between
407 incompleteness and miscategorisation errors for relevant columns.

408 **2.6. Summary measures and synthesis of results**

409 Results will be summarised narratively, and the characteristics and volume of evidence visualised in
410 interactive Tableau (Salesforce, Inc., 2025) dashboards, allowing quick access to the title and abstract
411 and link to included studies. Analyses may include publication and trends, geographical distribution of
412 studies per type of FPW or outcome and analyses of categories of effects under each type of impact.
413 This may include, where appropriate, reporting quantitative measures related to the volume or
414 proportion of the body of literature addressing specific aspects (e.g. specific items, or outcomes) but
415 quantitative synthesis of measure of effects are not envisaged. Dummy Tableau visualisations were
416 generated from the results of the data extraction piloting exercise. These illustrate how Tableau can
417 help visualise large amounts of data collected in a database and how interactivity can support reuse
418 and access to the collated references. This can be accessed here:

419 [https://public.tableau.com/views/ADLFGSEMdummy/DashboardMap2?:language=en-](https://public.tableau.com/views/ADLFGSEMdummy/DashboardMap2?:language=en-GB&:sid=&:redirect=auth&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)
420 [GB&:sid=&:redirect=auth&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link.](https://public.tableau.com/views/ADLFGSEMdummy/DashboardMap2?:language=en-GB&:sid=&:redirect=auth&:display_count=n&:origin=viz_share_link)

421

422 **2.7. Data Sharing**

423 The interactive Tableau dashboards will be hosted on Tableau Public a free online platform to share
424 interactive visualisations of public data. The underpinning database will also be made publicly
425 available as supplementary material to an open access peer-reviewed scientific article as an Excel file.

426

427 **2.8. Reporting**

428 A comprehensive written report, formatted as a peer-reviewed scientific article, will be developed to
429 accompany the systematic map visualizations. This report will ensure the study's results and database
430 are publicly accessible, downloadable, and easily searchable. It will document all phases of the

431 systematic mapping process, including the background and rationale for the study, details and
432 justifications for any deviations from the outlined methods, a summary of the evidence base's volume
433 and characteristics, and recommendations for future primary research to address identified knowledge
434 gaps. Additionally, the report will outline priorities and opportunities for future systematic reviews.
435 Significant priority will be given to adhering to established reporting standards for systematic maps,
436 such as the Reporting Standards for Systematic Evidence Syntheses (ROSES) guidelines (Haddaway et
437 al., 2018).

438

439

440 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

441 **Larisha Apete:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Validation,
442 Writing - original draft, and Writing - review & editing; **Joanne McPhie:** Methodology and Resources;
443 **Eleni Iacovidou:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Project administration,
444 Supervision, Validation, and Writing - review & editing; **Olwenn V. Martin:** Conceptualization, Data
445 curation, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Supervision, Validation,
446 and Writing - review & editing.

447

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451

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459 Expert Group. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial
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